

AI in Nigeria's Educational Future: True Cause for Alarm?

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Abstract: The apparent novelty of recent Artificial Intelligence (AI) research has elicited wide fascination and curiosity from the public, with many scholarly discussions. Like all previous innovations in science history, AI brings with it palpable fears concerning potential abuse or misapplication of the technology in various areas of human endeavour, including its implications for teaching and learning. Adopting the critical and historical methods of inquiry, this paper found that the misgivings about AI are not novel. It has been around since, at least, the Industrial Revolution of mid-eighteenth century, in the wake of which it was feared that machines were dangerous things that had come to replace the human work force, perform tasks even better, faster, and more efficiently than people. However, the embrace of mechanical technology at that age produced many positive results, such as technical knowledge, heightened productivity, large-scale production, wealth creation, job opportunities, and, of course, the advancement of human civilization. To this extent, the argument of this paper is that AI in information and communication is simply the latest phase of the continued evolution of human technological innovation; another stage of humanity's scientific journey, and ought to be embraced and adapted human wellbeing, because the advantages far outweigh any detriments. As such, Nigerian teachers and scholars must find ways to safely navigate this reality, and to appropriate the inherent advantages to the greatest possible extent through a process of knowledge evolution. The data used for this study were acquired from archival and secondary internet sources.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence (AI); education; human wellbeing; information and communication; language; science; technology*

INTRODUCTION

As the fast-paced developments in science and technology continue in the past century, it is hardly an exaggeration to suppose that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the most important burning issue across the world today, even in daily pedestrian discussions. In the past few years, artificial intelligence has been the major theme of most local and international academic seminars and conferences (AI Index Report, 2025). It is a phenomenon that has exerted a lot of impact on a broad range of disciplines and areas of human endeavour such as medicine, architecture, engineering, accounting, agriculture, visual and theatrical art, warfare, academic research, and education. As has been the case in every major past scientific breakthrough, the apparent sudden explosion of AI technology has brought with it palpable fears concerning the potential abuse or irresponsible application of this novel technology, once again, catalyzing heated debates in both academic and normal daily pedestrian interactions. The agitation is squarely hinged on the fact that artificial intelligence technology touches most directly on what is believed for centuries to be the essential difference between humans and machines, namely: intelligence. Accordingly, AI has been viewed as clear and present threat to human flourishing, particularly, as intelligence machines gradually replace human agents in different areas of skill deployment such as job performance, social activities, human relationships, and other things where natural human intelligence has hitherto held sway. The fear is that as machines replace people, it would get to a deplorable state in which humans themselves become

redundant as unwanted parasites, perhaps culminating in the disintegration of human civilization, as is known presently (Epoch Philosophy, 2023).

Accordingly, scholars in the education sector have engaged themselves in finding ways to safely navigate this reality in such a way as to steer clear of the inherent dangers, and ultimately achieve their basic mandate and purpose of ensuring that teaching and learning are not impeded by this state of affairs, but rather enhanced through the responsible and purpose-driven deployment of the benefits and advantages of artificial intelligence technology. Adopting the conceptual and critical methods, this paper found that both the radical growth of AI technology and social misgivings about it are not new. Rather, artificial intelligence is simply the extension or application of technology to new areas in which it did not exist before, such as the production of fake videos on social media and written documents, all of which now seem to falsify the traditional cliché that “seeing is believing”. But critical reflection and study quickly reveal that artificial intelligence - broadly conceived from the point of view technological innovation - has probably been around since, at least, the Industrial Revolution of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, during which it was also feared that machines were dangerous things that were being introduced to replace human beings and perform humans tasks much better, faster, and more efficiently than people. However, the eventual advent and embrace of machine technology by humanity not only widened the scope of production and productivity, but also advanced human civilization and knowledge economy (Core Knowledge Foundation, 2018). The argument of this paper, therefore, is that artificial intelligence is a welcome development that needs to be embraced and harnessed likewise for human wellbeing and advancement of human civilization, rather than feared and discarded. There are concerns that warrant careful consideration in the adoption of AI (Matthew and Isaac, 2025); but are these concerns more significant than the benefits which AI portends for Nigeria’s educational future?

Approaching AI from the angle of science and technology

The concept of *artificial intelligence* was initially adopted by the robotic scientist, John McCarthy, in 1955 to characterize “machines that behave as though they were intelligent” (cited in Ertel, 2017, p.1). As an area of study, it refers to the use of computer systems in carrying out complicated tasks normally reserved for human intelligence such as problem solving, teaching and learning, logical reasoning, and interpersonal communication. The term “intelligence” itself derives from two Latin expressions *intus* (between) and *legere* (to choose; to select) (Millar, 2021); that is, making a (right or appropriate) choice out of two or more available options. Intelligence presupposes being in the present; the ability to respond appropriately to novel or unprecedented situations, or happenstances, as determined by the occasion or circumstance in which an organism/agent finds itself. Intelligence is the ability to exercise brainpower in a spontaneous manner, to discern, comprehend, make decisions, and demonstrate skill and knowledge that are relevant to a given situation (Jackson, 1985). Essentially, intelligence is a matter of processing the available data, and following the cues, in the immediate and remote environment, to produce the effect or result that can be considered appropri-

ate or relevant to situation. In a nutshell, artificial intelligence is the production or creation of machines for the sole purpose of imitating (perhaps even surpassing) the most sophisticated human cognitive functions. This is why there are misgivings about its displacement of the human agency.

Perhaps, one way to dissipate the fears people have about artificial intelligence is to return to the basic notions of science and technology. The word, 'science', is a corollary from Latin etymology, *scientia*, which basically means knowledge. The *Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English* defines science as "knowledge about the world, especially based on examining, testing, and proving facts" (2014, p.261). That is, science is a means of knowing or understanding the physical world of human experience, to interpret and explain it correctly for human wellbeing. Science strives to explain or ease human understanding through the careful study of the universe. As a systematized body of knowledge, or the means thereof, science is best described as a system by which the natural or physical world order is explored and made adaptable for the wellbeing of humanity. Essentially, the goal of science is to promote an understanding of the general principles underlying the functioning of the universe.

There are many ways of gaining knowledge of the world and interpreting human experience; some of them include religion, culture and tradition, intuition, divination, astrology, and mental reflection (Copi and Cohen, 1994). What makes science distinct from the rest is that science is based on the use of data collected by physical experience, observation, experimentation and peer verification, all of which show what the universe is and how it operates (Hurley, 2012). This means that science principally focuses on phenomena that can be measured, observed, recorded, or detected. Science is, therefore, not a matter of belief, opinion, faith, or tradition, in the sense of there being some absolute authority upon which it must be based; rather, science is a matter of conclusive evidence that can be subjected to the acid test of experimentation, critical thinking, logic, and peer review.

Following from this, it goes without needing to be said that natural science is not equipped to deal with subjective phenomena, such as those commonly found in world religions, philosophies of life, cultural traditions, the ultimate purpose of life, the afterlife, the existence of God and other supernatural realities, questions of good and evil, human destiny, and the human soul. Scientific attempts to deal with such supernatural questions have almost always ended in bland reductionism that eventually leaves more questions than answers. This is not surprising; natural science is resolutely riveted on the physical realm of human experience and tends to dismiss the supernatural as extraneous superstition. Natural science simply does not have the means to settle supernatural questions because such issues lie beyond the natural or physical order of things which science is expressly designed for. Thus, answers to questions that go beyond the natural world must ultimately be sought in religion, philosophy, culture, and other belief systems.

The open competition of ideas by which the scientific enterprise is characterized directly aids objectivity, since every scientific proposition is laid open to everyone in the scientific community willing to verify or investigate for themselves. Based on this verification principle, scientific propositions are typically said to be true or false, depending on whether they corre-

spond to facts or not; also, any scientific proposition must be such that it can be falsified, that is, made true or false (Popper, 2002). By virtue of this last point, any statement or proposition that fails to meet this criterion may be considered unscientific.

However, due to the dynamic nature of the phenomenon of knowledge, science is not a closed enterprise. Rather, it is open-ended in the sense that it is always in progress. It is an on-going enterprise, whose truth is entirely dependent on new developments and further discoveries. As such, we can say that scientific findings are mainly tentative, and there is nothing absolute about them in the same way that religious and cultural knowledge claims, for instance, are said to be dogmatic, closed and absolute. Scientific ideas and knowledge are always in a state of flux, and open to revision and modification, or even outright rejection, in the light of new developments (Hurley, 2012).

Science has developed in such a way that its applications have tremendously benefited humanity in all kinds of ways. The first notable value of science is that it satisfies human practical needs. Through the development of modern technology, science makes possible an easier and more abundant life humanity. Indeed, science and technology have been put to bad use that brought disastrous consequences for humankind, such as the atomic bomb, nuclear weaponry and warfare, Hitler's Holocaust, environmental pollution, deforestation, and other man-made disasters. However, values of science are incalculable. For instance, advances in medical sciences and machine technology have enabled the production of more food and understanding and treatment of formerly terminal diseases and illnesses, thus making it possible for humans to live longer and more meaningfully to the extent that would have been impossible. The second point is that science is knowledge and, thus, an end in itself. We cannot live meaningfully without first knowing something about how the world operates. Hence, another intrinsic value of science is its ability to satisfy human intellectual curiosity, the fulfilment of the primordial human desire to know (Copi and Cohen, 1994). In this regard, Odozor (2015a, p.60) notes that:

The ability of science to solve human existential problems - however successfully - stems from the fact that nature is observable and predictable, and produces similar result under the same conditions. This, in turn, makes human knowledge possible. Since nature behaves in certain predictable ways, we have, by applying inductive reasoning on past experience, been able to understand some aspects of it, and, thereby, built our entire knowledge system on that basis. Ultimately, if nature had been totally unpredictable, science would be absolutely impossible, as we would know virtually nothing with certainty.

The third value of science lies in its power of explanation. Science does not consist merely in the accumulation of facts; beyond that, it seeks to understand how these facts relate to each other in the bigger picture of human experience. With the data, science can explain the world and, so, expand the frontiers of human knowledge. Thus, science can as well serve as an explanatory tool in the hand of the scientist due to its immediacy of reliability and practicality.

In the discussion of the values of science above, it was pointed out that the first value of science is its ability to satisfy human practical needs, by making possible an easier and more abundant life. How scientific applications have tremendously benefited humanity was highlighted; also, the fact that the result of scientific endeavour is the development of relevant technologies to address the practical problems of the human situation. Examples of these concrete and practical benefits include airplanes, telephones, automobiles, computers, electricity, space-going vehicles, ocean liners like ships, information and communication technology, and recently, artificial intelligence.

All these have enabled human beings to live more fulfilling and abundant lives than before they were discovered or invented through the study of science (Copi and Cohen, 1994). Airplanes, for instance, solve the problem of distance, making it possible for people to save time by carrying out trips that would have taken months within hours. With telephones people no longer worry about being physically present with their friends, colleagues and family, especially when it is beyond their control. Computers solve the problem of data management in a way that is unprecedented in all human history. Science and technology have made life more meaningful and worthwhile. This is true, even though science and technology have also been put to negative uses portending disastrous consequences, for example, nuclear and biological weaponry or warfare, environmental pollution, Hitler's Holocaust, global warming and the continued reckless oil spillage in the Niger Delta.

To this extent, then, science and technology go hand in hand, because without prior scientific understanding and knowledge, it would be virtually impossible to develop the relevant technology that would solve a given problem either at the individual or social level of human existence. Hence, technology is the application of scientific knowledge in order to identify and solve problems in various areas of human existence and fields of endeavour. Although technology is based on developments and findings in science, the former is simply an attempt to proffer solutions to the problems and difficulties faced by human beings in the various spheres of their interaction with one another and with the physical world. This is the inroad by which artificial intelligence gains timely and relevant entry into human affairs and endeavour.

Apprehension and misgiving about scientific and technological breakthroughs and their potential harm to human wellbeing and future is not a new phenomenon. Several decades into the Industrial Revolution in Britain, there arose a group of protesting men known as Luddites, who literally went about destroying factories and the newly invented machines in them, in the futile attempt to hold off the hands of technological progress. One case in point that took place in early 19th century is described as follows:

Just around midnight, twelve masked men broke down a door and ran shouting into a dark factory: "Long live King Ludd! Long live our king!" Swinging lead pipes and hammers, they attacked the weaving machines with such fury you might have thought the machines were evil monsters. ... After they finished, the men set the building on fire. It was 1812. The Luddites had struck again. Why did these desperate Englishmen think that weaving machines were their enemies? What had happened to them? Who was King Ludd, anyway? The answers

to these questions have to do with a protest movement against industrialization (The Core Knowledge Foundation, 2018, p.60).

The European Industrial Revolution naturally bifurcated human society into two groups consisting of winners and losers. Winners are the investor owners of factories and the class of workers who were able to adapt to the novelty by upgrading their knowledge to be able to operate the machines that had now replaced manual labour. On the other hand, the losers were mostly unskilled workers whose numbers were inadvertently replaced by machines. They developed a passionate hatred for machines and industries and saw the Industrial Revolution as a terrible evil that must be met with extreme measures. But the underlying truth is that they failed to adapt to the industrialization process of machine production, even as they blamed their predicament on the change that besieged them on all sides (Easton et al., 2023). Still, the extreme measures taken by rebels like the Luddites produced the remarkable impact of forcing the British parliament to overhaul the labour laws that ultimately improved the lot of industry workers and the conditions of service in the following decade. In all, industrialization opened job opportunities, enhanced productivity and economic development, and helped move human civilization forward through technological innovation. Within three generations, the population of Britain quadrupled from 8 million to about 32.5 million, as many people in London went from rural living to becoming urban dwellers.

Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* published in 1818 comes to mind as one of the classical depictions of the extent to which the human imagination can run wild on the fear of technology. The novel is a portrayal of what could go wrong when man-made machines become self-aware and defy control, turn against their producer or programmer, and overrun the planet. What Shelley succeeded in doing is to impress vividly upon public consciousness the fact that scientists could only control the production of machines but could hardly determine what happens thereafter. Even the well-intentioned machines have the potential to transform into "cold-blooded monsters" because of their "mindless" nature; because they lack soul or conscience, inbuilt mechanisms that nature confers on real humans to ensure the corporate survival and continuation of the human civilization. Similarly, the escalation of robotic engineering in the past several decades has seen a concomitant rise in the fear that robots were beginning to take over the jobs of real people and would, with time, overrun the planet, taking over power from humans and their institutions. An online commentator (@Celis.C, 2024) notably puts it this way:

As someone who works in robotics, I often wonder about the repercussions of my labour. I have reached a point where I can actually see the consequences of my work too. There is something sublime in automation's ability to appeal to a utopia that could be, but is marred by the late-stage society we live in today. That said, [the] view that this deconstructs the culture surrounding capitalism, is very emboldening.

Scholars across various disciplines have made entire career debating the ethics of technological innovations, raising different kinds of controversies in the process, and ultimately forming and leading public opinion. There is considerable discussion among scholars concerning hu-

man cloning (Watson, 1971; Rifkin, 2005), stem cell research (Nickel, 2008), digital nativity (Reynolds, 2015), and others from a wide range of topics and interests.

Educational advantages and prospects of AI

The benefits of artificial intelligence in education are multiple. However, only a handful of them will be outlined here, to demonstrate that the advantages far outweigh whatever the problems are, in as much as the intentions are genuinely educational. The first potential advantage of AI is that it makes possible personalized learning, because it is flexible by nature and easily adaptable to the specific needs of the individual learner (Akyuz, 2022). This used to be rather tasking and challenging to the traditional methods of classroom instruction, where the teacher must meet each individual pupil or student, and patiently guide them towards their learning goals. But with AI, the learning process and content are tailored to meet each child where they are in the learning process, according to their individual capabilities, pace, and time frame,

For those who receive requisite training and are both open to learning and can exercise the necessary discipline, AI enhances teacher productivity and efficiency, as well as good time management. With AI to sort out grading of students' scores in examinations, the teacher has enough time at his disposal to devote to study, research and dissemination of research findings to students and the community in the appropriate manner and measure required to create lasting impact. These are the more fundamental aspects of the teacher's job, and lead to improved assessment and feedback mechanisms.

AI also facilitates increased access to quality education, especially in rural areas where there is internet connectivity. In truth, many villages and communities in Nigeria suffer connectivity issues from time to time, due to poor infrastructure. But the fact is that once this barrier is removed, either by the deliberate intervention of a willing government, or the decisive initiative of the hardworking student, AI is readily available online almost in equal measure as it is for residents in the urban districts with relatively reliable network and stable internet connection. In other words, the weakest link of AI, namely, poor connectivity that creates a gulf between the urban centers and rural areas, is precisely its strongest link, as all that is needed is the effort and the ability to overcome the challenge of poor connectivity.

One of the most ridiculous, and yet most popular, objections to the evolution of AI technology is the argument that it is the source of deep fakes: fake news, inauthentic videos, plagiarism, for example, capable of misleading people. But there are a few facts that render this objection impotent. First, fake news, doctored or tailored videos, plagiarism and the likes have been around for long before the advent of AI technology; in fact, they still exist today, with or without AI. AI is merely an additional tool to the collection of items that can be used by unscrupulous individuals and groups to carry out the mischief of producing and disseminating false information. AI may facilitate and quicken the process, but it is merely a tool and must be used by a human agent in a certain way before problems arise. In fact, AI makes it even more possible, and much easier in today's world, to verify the authenticity of digital products.

Before the escalation of artificial intelligence technology, local and international media outlets had been in the business of broadcasting false, unverified news items, for which they had had to deal with lawsuits. In many of these cases, the damage would have been done even if, and by the time, such information was recalled and apology tendered. Some of the false news take the form of half-truths that have been carefully crafted to achieve some hidden political and ideological agenda. For example, the BBC has been recently indicted for doctoring its reportage of President Trump's speech of 6 January 2021, to suggest that Trump had called for violence (Nanji, 2025). Other international news outlets, such as the *CNN* and *MSNBC* in the United States are renowned for promoting the ideals of the left political divide, while others, such as *Fox News* and *Newsmax* identify with the conservative, right-wing approach to news coverage. In Nigeria, there is no doubt about the loyalty of the NTA, state-owned media, and many of the private news outlets, such as TVC, Channels TV, AIT, *The Nation Newspaper*, and *The Sun*, to their respective owners. These outlets would never take on any news item likely to diminish the political leanings and interests of their stakeholders. Few media in Nigeria today are truly independent, free and neutral.

Secondly, AI is merely a tool; and every tool can be harnessed towards good and evil ends, depending on the motive and intention of the human agent, as noted. There is an important distinction between the reality of a thing, its good use, and its abuse or misuse; some of the misgivings about the evolution of AI technology fail to take this distinction into cognizance. Such objections suggest that AI is an intrinsically bad thing that should be jettisoned outright, almost like throwing the baby out with the bath water. A kitchen knife, for example, is a most important tool without which it would be impossible to navigate one's way around the kitchen; on the other hand, it is also potentially a most dangerous weapon in the hand of an unskilled user, or even an attacker (Odozor, 2015b). The same is true for all other things, tools and technologies, ranging from the internet, computer systems, houses, cars, nuclear and atomic energies, food, and, of course, AI technology, which can be deployed to serve good and ulterior purposes, depending entirely on misuse or overdependence by the human agent. Just as AI may be used to produce fake content, it can equally be used to design visual aid materials to facilitate and enhance learning and knowledge.

There is a distinction between a fair use of AI and overdependence on it. Addressing the context of journalism on the fair use of AI, as a case study, the Atlanta-based Nigerian social critic, Farooq Kperogi notes that "AI can assist with distilling complex reports, interpreting intricate statistical data, suggesting headlines, enhancing grammar and style without erasing a writer's distinctive voice, and even sparking story ideas" (Kperogi, 2025, par.7). Overdependence, on the other hand, is when an individual outsources every task that needs to be performed by them to artificial intelligence algorithms. When a person relies exclusively or entirely on artificial intelligence modules for every major task and every single purpose, including reasoning, writing, communicating, and answering questions, then creativity would be adversely affected in the process. Again, Kperogi writes:

In recent months, I've noticed a troubling trend: more and more journalists are outsourcing not just their writing but their thinking to AI. The outcome is often dull, colorless, formulaic prose that reflects the homogenizing influence of American English and its creeping linguistic imperialism (par.8).

As technology exists, in the first place, to solve potential problems, so AI is technology that comes, for the most part, with inbuilt solutions to its own problems. For example, there are AI tools that can be used to detect and take down plagiarism, fake news and videos. One of the most popular ones is the Turnitin Plagiarism Scan software, currently used in many universities and higher institutions not merely to check the originality of students' thesis, but also to ascertain the precise level of authenticity of such works. Others in this category include CopyLeaks, Scribbr, Grammarly, Originality AI, Winston AI, and Quilbot. These tools deploy advanced algorithms that scan prospective documents against an entire universe of webpages and online publications for AI-generated content plagiarisms, and text that may have been adapted from language models. WhatsApp has an inbuilt facility specifically used for factchecking and determining the veracity or otherwise of posts made by consumers across its platforms. This is called *research* in academic circles and exists precisely for the sole purpose of curbing misinformation and promoting clarity. Yet detractors of AI technology speak as though humans were incapable of carrying out simple background checks, even where doubt exists. Just as research is done to throw light on intellectual matters, it can also be applied with regards to AI technology and its adoption in every area of human endeavour. In each case, what human beings basically do is to focus on the substance and disregard what is extraneous. As Dewey thoughtfully puts it:

[When] the practical meaning of the [moral] situation—that is to say the action needed to satisfy it—is not self-evident, it has to be searched for. [When] there are conflicting desires and alternative apparent goods, what is needed is to find the right [one], the right good (1957, p.163-64).

This consideration is parallel to what happens in research work. A researcher does not take the intuition and immediate sensory perception as sole basis for knowledge; rather, research involves spending a lot of time, peering into other information sources, to produce knowledge that will be worthy of the name. In the same way, AI content should not be simply appropriated without background check; rather, they require some rigorous and patient research, considering that social media narratives are constantly modified beyond recognition, sometimes even completely upturned and thrown overboard.

Above all, training of teachers on how to manually detect AI using their natural intelligence and sensitization of learners on the pitfalls of outsourcing their learning responsibilities and duties to AI are both also available. Such training enhances expertise in the detection and avoidance of plagiarism and doctored contents, as Kperogi testifies:

I ... have formal certification in detecting AI writing and have also systematically studied the unique stylistic imprints of AI writing on my own. I can tell with 99% confidence when a piece of prose is AI-generated (2025, par.5).

Kperogi then narrates the following experiment with his students:

After a bad experience with a previous graduate class I taught, I introduced an "AI detection in writing" module, where we read articles about tell-tale signs of AI writing, research the decline in the cognitive abilities of people who are AI-dependent in their writing and thought processes, etc. It worked wonders! Students developed an impressively stone-cold disdain for AI writing, heightened their sensitivity

to AI-generated writing (so that months after the semester, some of them still send me the AI-generated content they encounter on social media and elsewhere, complete with laughter emojis), and, of course, no one used AI to write. I encourage them to use AI to generate ideas, develop outlines of ideas, and to create rough drafts that serve as inspiration to create their own work, but not as a substitute for writing and thinking (par. 25-27).

In fact, sometimes such training is even altogether unnecessary. People can tell when a content is AI-generated simply from experience, with their sense organs and their intellect. The reason is simple: the content is *artificial* and *simulated*, and not natural in the way real life contents are natural to a casual observer.

Much of the distaste for AI is based on the spurious assumption that its adoption in teaching and learning automatically implies jettisoning the traditional instruction method *in toto*. But this is flatly untrue. Nothing in the use of AI for teaching or learning potentially suggests this or takes it for granted. In fact, over the past decade, studies have tended to indicate that the combination of personalized learning strategy and the traditional method of instruction has tended to reduce students' learning time and enhanced their academic performance (Hotomaroglu, 2012; Guyah, 2021).

Every bad thing that results from the adoption of AI is, in the end, traceable to human agents, and not to AI in itself. AI is not intrinsically evil. Rather, what one needs to worry about is AI getting in hands of the wrong human agent, in the same way people in modern society today worry about proliferation of light arms among non-state actors, or about nuclear materials being in the possession of wrong individuals and groups. Thankfully, with AI, the human person can be reasoned with; she is neither a robot nor a machine, but a human individual in flesh and blood living in the moment. This is precisely where the ethics of AI plays its crucial role, as an area of study and research specifically designed to address the potential problems arising from the design and adoption of artificial intelligence.

Existing AI initiatives in Nigerian education sector include the Neo Cloud Learning Institute in Abuja, which is a comprehensive AI program whose aim is to equip aspiring professionals in various fields with the skills they need in their chosen areas of specialization. Another one is the Practical Artificial Intelligence Development Foundation, more commonly known as Nigeria Foundation for Artificial Intelligence (NFAI). This community is dedicated to driving innovation in Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Nigeria's development. Third is the Nigeria AI Scaling Hub; a multi-stakeholder initiative that will coordinate the scaling of mature AI solutions in the country (Tunji, 2025). In December 2023, the Nigerian AI Research Scheme stepped up its game by offering 5 million Naira (about \$6,444) to 45 new AI businesses and researchers (Nwaokocha, 2023). It aims to harness to potentiality of AI applications for economic prosperity. Focus areas include agriculture, education, finance, governance, healthcare, and sustainability.

As has been demonstrated above, the fears and sentiments associated with the evolution and deployment of artificial intelligence have been around since, at least, the Industrial Revolution (1700s and 1800s). Loss of jobs and other fears derive their apparent legitimacy from the fear of the unknown; but such misgivings have, *ab initio*, been forestalled by the creation and upgrade of more job opportunities, plus advancement of human civilization, even within the Industrial Revolution and the contemporary advancement of AI technology. Studies such as that of Appiah, et al. (2022), argue for the expansion of opportunities in the wake of AI explosion; opportunities available only to those who are adequately trained and favourably disposed towards new developments. According to a recent UN report (2025), the AI market is projected to hit \$4.8tn by 2033 in earnings, as dominant frontier technology. With these possibilities, it is clearly irrational that mere misgivings about AI should stop this colossal sum of money from getting into the pockets of those who are willing to take the plunge into the vast opportunities that AI makes possible in the next decade.

AI is simply a technology, that is, a tool. Every tool has both good and bad uses, advantages and disadvantages. What humans have always done from the dawn of their evolutionary history is to adapt: ditch the bad, and adopt the good. AI will be no different. Most attention in both scholarly and pedestrian discussions focuses on INTELLIGENCE and ignores the ARTIFICIAL aspect. This fact is quite revealing, because it betrays the truth, namely that AI will ultimately depend on the natural human agent (algorithm, coding, programming). The “garbage-in-garbage-out” principle/cliché will still apply, despite the emotions currently being raised by artificial intelligence technology. Ultimately, fears about AI, though legitimate due to the novelty involved, will eventually peter out when the novelty wears off. To this end, another online commentator (@Celis.C., 2024) makes the following critical observation:

People fear losing their jobs - and jobs in general - because society has been designed around people being forced to have one for an income to survive. What technology could do is do the work for us so we don't have to work (as much), and enjoy the fruits of technology's labour. The reason this never happened is because ALL PROFITS STAY IN PRIVATE HANDS. This is [the real] inhumane practice.

Conclusion

Technology is the practical application of scientific knowledge obtained from observing how nature operates. Every technology is designed to complement nature. Like all technology, AI intends to enhance and facilitate nature and fill the gaps or shortcomings of nature. Hence, AI is technology at its most basic level of analysis. Therefore, AI is not altogether new, but basically the latest phase in the history and development of science and technology.

For its own part, the government can intervene in a number of ways by creating level playing ground so that there will be equitable access to AI-powered education, by promoting teacher competence, training, and capacity building, and by establishing robust regulatory frameworks and policies to enhance transparency, accountability, and constant evaluation of AI systems. Stakeholders' focus must be on the transformative potentials of AI in education, not merely on the potential dangers. Such fears are almost always negative in impact because they

cripple productivity. Stakeholders reserve the collective responsibility to close this lacuna through a call to action by harnessing the benefits of AI, without trivializing or failing to address the concerns and fears of the public as and when due. AI has come to stay and cannot be wished away. The way forward is to get the human resources factor right through adequate training and ethical orientation, and to deal with the novelty; to incorporate both factors into usefulness, to take advantage of the deliverables that AI technology portends. As in evolutionary/biological adaptation, the key is, Adapt or go out of business! AI research and innovations must begin by putting humanity's wellbeing and that of the rest of nature at the centre; and this is where the relevance of the humanities come into play, so scientific and technological endeavour attain its purpose of making the human experience a better one, rather than a nightmare.

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